

Yield potential

Heritability of primary root length

N. G. Hajra, S. G. Hajra, RRII, North Eastern Research Complex, P.O. Kunjaban, Tripura 799006; and P. Bairagi, Botany Department, Burdwan University, Burdwan 713104, India

In rice, as in most cereals, root systems show high variability because the genes controlling them come under environmental influences. We crossed 11 varieties having good and poor root systems and obtained 7 cross-combinations. Seedlings were grown in test tubes with White's medium. Primary root length was recorded at 28 d and different parameters estimated to indicate the nature and degree of improvement by hybridization in F₂ generation. CH1040/ NC918 and CH47/CH63 were relatively stable, with low response to environment. The five other crosses were highly responsive to environmental fluctuations, requiring

repeated selection in advanced generations of the best 5% of the population.

The F₂ lines provide a prediction of the genetic advance, or improvement

expected. The primary root length showed a moderately high heritability in each cross (82.4 to 52.3%), although the estimated numbers of effective factors were low (see table). □

Genetic parameters of primary root length in 7 rice crosses.

Parameter ^a	Larkoch/ NC918	CH10/ NC918	CH1040/ NC918	CH47/ CH63	CH988/ CHI7	Badkalamkati 65/CH4	Boak/ NC918
<i>Mean (cm)</i>							
\bar{P}_1	8.73	10.80	9.13	11.13	10.93	18.03	15.07
\bar{P}_2	18.80	18.80	18.80	20.73	17.27	18.43	18.80
$(\bar{P}_1 + \bar{P}_2) / 2$	13.77	14.80	13.97	15.93	14.10	18.33	16.53
\bar{F}_1	14.80	13.70	13.60	19.30	19.00	18.68	16.10
\bar{F}_2	15.80	14.00	12.30	16.20	20.01	22.03	19.47
<i>Variance</i>							
VP ₁	3.86	4.29	3.38	3.64	5.26	5.59	4.46
VP ₂	5.23	5.23	5.23	6.00	5.86	5.54	5.23
VE	4.54	4.76	4.30	4.82	5.56	5.01	4.34
VF ₂	25.83	12.27	9.04	11.43	18.73	14.08	12.38
VG	21.28	7.51	4.74	6.60	13.17	9.07	7.54
GA	8.63	4.42	3.25	4.02	6.27	4.98	4.41
<i>Heritability</i>							
h ² (%)	82.4	6.20	52.39	57.78	10.30	64.41	60.88
<i>Estimated effective factors</i>							
K	0.59 ≈ 1	1.07 ≈ 1	2.46 ≈ 2	1.74 ≈ 2	0.38 ≈ 0	0	0.23 = 0

^aVG = genetic variance, GA = genetic advance, VP₁ and VP₂ = variation of first and second parents, VE = environmental-variance, VF₂ = variation of F₂ population, \bar{P}_1 and \bar{P}_2 = av root length of parent one and two, \bar{F}_1 and \bar{F}_2 = av primary root length of F₁ and F₂ hybrids.

Rice panicle characteristics

S. Mallik A. M. Aguilar, and B. S. Vergara, Plant Physiology Department, IIRI

We studied panicle characteristics of 10 IR varieties, 16 *O. glaberrima* accessions, and 16 lines from a cross involving upland rice parents. High

density (HD) grains, having specific gravity >1.20, are found mostly on primary branches of rice panicles. Increasing the percentage of HD grains by decreasing the number of secondary branches can increase rice yield potential. The number of HD grains may also improve with better delivery system of the assimilates, such as more

vascular bundles, and bigger culms or thicker culms.

The *glaberrimas* had comparatively more primary branches and more spikelets on primary branches than did IR and upland entries (Table 1). They also had fewer secondary branches—the location of most low density grains—and fewer spikelets on them. □

Table 1. Range and mean of 10 panicle characters in 3 types of rice varieties. IIRI, 1988.

Character	Range			Mean		
	IR varieties	O. glaberrima	Upland	IR varieties	O. glaberrima	Upland
1. Primary branches (no.) (Pbr)	7 - 16.3	8 - 16.3	7.7- 14.7	10.3 ± 0.7	13.1 ± 0.7	12.1 ± 0.5
2. Spikelets on Pbr (no.) (SPbr)	37 -124	51 -139	38.3- 91.3	60.2 ± 7.5	99.3 ± 7.0	70.6 ± 3.7
3. Secondary branches (no.) (Sbr)	18.8- 34.8	2.2- 27.7	5.7- 39	26.7 ± 2.0	12.8 ± 1.9	27 ± 2.8
4. Spikelets on Sbr (no.) (SSbr)	60.3-117	4.7- 59.7	12.3-130.7	87.3 ± 6.4	33.2 ± 5.6	85 ± 9.6
5. Total spikelets (no.) (TSP)	100 -241	91 -199	51 -208	147.5 ± 12.2	132.4 ± 7.2	155.5 ± 12.7
6. Inner vascular bundle (no.) (IVB)	14 - 25.5	13.7- 18.7	9 - 22.7	19.9 ± 1.1	15.8 ± 0.4	16.0 ± 0.9
7. Outer vascular bundle (no.) (OVB)	16.8- 30.5	17.3- 36	13.7- 34.5	21 ± 1.2	34.1 ± 9.3	24.8 ± 1.7
8. Culm diameter (mm) (CD)	2.1- 3.2	1.6- 2.6	1.3- 3	2.3 ± 0.1	2 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.1
9. Air space (mm) (Asp)	1.5- 2.4	0.8- 1.8	0.6- 2.1	1.7 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1
10. Culm thickness ^a (mm) (Cth)	0.3- 0.4	0.3- 0.5	0.3- 0.6	0.3 ± 0.01	0.4 ± 0.01	0.4 ± 0.02

^aCth = (CD - ASP)/2.

The three types differed little in total spikelet number, indicating that panicles with more primary branches and fewer secondary branches can be obtained without reducing total spikelets per panicle. IR varieties had more inner vascular bundles from just below the neck node and *glaberrimas* had more outer vascular bundles. Culm diameter and air space did not vary widely, but culms were thinner in IR varieties.

Correlation coefficients (Table 2) among characters show that primary

branch number was significantly correlated with number of spikelets on primary branch, total spikelets, and inner vascular bundle. In upland lines, culm thickness was correlated with all characters except number of inner vascular bundle. Culm thickness might prove to be a useful overall measure of desirable traits.

Breeding programs should transfer useful traits of *glaberrimas* and upland lines into IR varieties to increase the number of HD grains. □

Table 2. Phenotypic interrelationship between different panicle characters in 3 types of rice varieties.^a IRRI, 1988.

	1 Pbr			2 SPbr			3 Sbr		
	a	b	c	a	b	c	a	b	c
2.SPbr	.97**	.96**	.98**						
3.Sbr	.59	-.46	.77**	.49	-.34	.81**			
4.SSbr	.65*	-.46	.77**	.55	-.36	.80**	.94**	.99**	.99**
5.TSP	.93**	.56*	.86**	.90**	.68**	.89**	.79**	.45	.98**
6.IVB	.80**	.60*	.91**	.69*	.62*	.87**	.67*	.04	.54**
7.OVB	.95**	-.02	.83**	.93**	.05	.79**	.61	-.19	.73**
8.CD	.89**	.11	.89**	.85**	.24	.87**	.68*	.38	.83**
9.ASp	.85**	.15	.88**	.77**	.27	.85**	.72*	.34	.73**
10.Cth	.60	-.80**	.61*	.74*	-.05	.58*	.02	.12	.82**
	4 SSbr			5 TSP			6 IVB		
	a	b	c	a	b	c	a	b	c
2.SPbr									
3.Sbr									
4.SSbr									
5.TSP	.86**	.44	.98**						
6.IVB	.79**	.02	.54*	.83*	.61*	.66**			
7.OVB	.68*	-.21	.71**	.93**	-.12	.76**	.82**	-.29	.74**
8.CD	.71*	.37	.83**	.89**	.52*	.88**	.80**	.53*	.80**
9.ASp	.75*	.31	.74**	.86**	.51*	.81**	.81**	.62*	.83**
10.Cth	.20	.15	.82**	.56	.06	.79**	.43	-.15	.41
	7 OVB			8 CD			9 ASP		
	a	b	c	a	b	c	a	b	c
2.SPbr									
3.Sbr									
4.SSbr									
5.TSP									
6.IVB									
7.OVB									
8.CD	.94**	-.12	.75**						
9.ASp	.90**	-.07	.68**	.97**	.89**	.97**			
10.Cth	.63	-.12	.71**	.53	.30	.71**	.36	-.15	.53*

^a a = IR varieties, b = *O. glaberrima*, c = upland lines. *, ** = significant at 5% and 1% levels of probability, respectively.

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Flowering behavior of photoperiodsensitive rice germplasm of Bangladesh

Md. E. Haque, A. Baset, Z. Zeenat, and N. M. Miah, Plant Breeding Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), P.O. BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh

Most traditional transplanted aman rice varieties of Bangladesh are photoperiod-sensitive; however, sensitivity varies with variety and location.

Nearly 1,050 photoperiod-sensitive germplasm were grown in 1987 transplanted aman season in the BRRI experimental field (latitude 24°N) to observe flowering behavior. Materials were seeded on 20 Jul and transplanted on 22 Aug.

Varieties flowered from 15 Oct to 25 Nov (see figure). More varieties (395) flowered 1-5 Nov, synchronized with the strongly photoperiod-sensitive local variety Nizersail. Varieties flowering before 1 Nov could be moderately sensitive or have a long critical photoperiod. Those flowering later could be very strongly sensitive to photoperiod or have a short critical photoperiod. Another group of weakly photoperiod-sensitive varieties in Bangladesh flowering from late Sep to mid-Oct is not included here.

Distribution of varieties by date of flowering. BRRI, Bangladesh, 1987.